

Understanding Tephritids in Toto: Taxonomy, Ecology, Quarantine & Management

Abstracts

Edited by

P.D. Kamala Jayanthi
A.K. Chakravarthy
T. Raghava
Vivek Kempuraj

27th May, 2016

Indian Institute of Horticultural Research
Hessaraghatta , Bengaluru

Kalshani

**Host plant resistance (HPR) study on snapmelon
(*Cucumis melo* var. *momordica*) against melon
fruit fly (*Bactrocera cucurbitae* (Coquillett)) in arid
region Rajasthan**

Shravan M Haldhar

ICAR-Central Institute for Arid Horticulture, Beechwal,

Bikaner-334006

Corresponding author email ID: haldhar80@gmail.com

The 43 snapmelon genotypes were taken for preliminary screening against *B. cucurbitae* and significant differences were found in percentage fruit infestation and larval density per fruit. The larval density per fruit had a significant positive correlation with percentage fruit infestation ($r = 0.988$; $P < 0.01$). The genotypes IC-430190, DKS-AHS 2011/4, DKS-AHS 2011/3 and IC-430176 were found resistant whereas IC-430154, IC-430155, IC-430156, IC-430157, IC-430158, IC-430159, IC-430161, IC-430164, IC-430168, IC-430169, IC-430170, IC-430171, IC-430172, IC-430177, IC-430178, IC-430182, IC-430183, IC-430184, IC-430186, IC-430187 and DKS-AHS 2011/1 were the susceptible genotypes against melon fruit fly. The percentage fruit infestation increased with an increase in larval density per fruit and there was a significant positive correlation ($r = 0.988$; $P < 0.01$) between per cent fruit infestation and larval density per fruit. In pooled data, the per cent fruit infestation was highest in IC-430184 (69.67 %) and lowest in IC-430190 (11.21 %) followed by DKS-AHS-2011/4 (14.97 %). The larval density ranged from 8.63 to 17.57 and 8.30 to 17.20 larvae per

fruit in the rainy, 2014 and summer, 2015, respectively. In pooled data, the larval density was maximum in IC-430169 (17.37 larvae per fruit) and minimum in IC-430190 (8.47 larvae per fruit) followed by DKS-AHS 2011/3 (8.8 larvae per fruit). The percentage fruit infestation and the larval density per fruit with free amino acid (0.97 & 0.96) and TSS (0.3 & 0.3) of fruit had a significant positive correlation whereas; Flavonoid (-0.98 & -0.96), tannins (-0.97 & -0.95), phenols (-0.96 & -0.95) and total alkaloid (-0.97 & -0.94) had significant negative correlation. The length of ovary pubescence (-0.99 & -0.96), rind hardness at immature stage (-0.93 & -0.90), rind hardness at mature stage (-0.59 & -0.54) and pericarp thickness (-0.78 & -0.75) had significant negative correlations whereas; flesh thickness (0.62 & 0.61), fruit length (0.61 & 0.62) and fruit diameter (0.76 & 0.77) had significant positive correlations with the percentage fruit infestation and the larval density per fruit. Basis on Kaiser Normalization method, the extraction communalities for all the variables tested were $e = 0.5$ indicating that the variables were well represented by the extracted PCs which together explained a cumulative variation of 82.8 %. PC1 explained 53.41 % of the variation while PC2 explained 29.39 % of variation. PC1 had the loadings for flavonoid content (0.86), tannins content (0.88), total alkaloid (0.82), phenols content (0.88), free amino acid (-0.83), total soluble solid (-0.66), length of ovary pubescence (0.88), pericarp thickness (0.67) and rind hardness at immature stage (0.89). Rind hardness at mature stage (0.52), flesh thickness (-0.74), fruit length (-0.86) and fruit diameter (-0.68) were loaded in PC2. The flavonoid, total alkaloid, tannins, phenols content, length of ovary pubescence and rind hardness were the novel antibiosis and antixenotic

Understanding Tephritids in Toto:

Taxonomy, Ecology, Quarantine & Management
May 27, 2016 IHR, Bangalore.

ABSTRACTS

characters found in snapmelon which were resistant to fruit fly. These above snapmelon genotypes could be used in future breeding programme as resistant sources.

Key Words: cucurbit fruit fly, antixenosis, antitoxis.

Understanding Tephritids in Toto:

Taxonomy, Ecology, Quarantine & Management
May 27, 2016 IHR, Bangalore.

ABSTRACTS

Does fertilization of *Bactrocera cucurbitae* eggs initiate primary defense response in *Secchium edule* fruit?

P. D. Kamala Jayanthi & Vivek Kempuraj

National Fellow Lab, Division of Entomology and Nematology, Indian Institute of Horticultural Research, Hessaraghatta Lake Post, Bangalore – 560 089, India.

Corresponding authors email ID: jainsect@gmail.com

Plants recognize insect oviposition and elicit defenses against the eggs to curtail future herbivory. But, how plants recognize oviposition and initiate defense response is a controversial subject. In order to determine the mechanism of ignition of primary defense response in insect-plant interaction, we used the oviposition behavior of *Bactrocera cucurbitae* on *Secchium edule* as a model system. Female insect fertilizes their eggs during oviposition. Previous studies have shown that an oxidative blast takes place during fertilization of eggs and hydrogen peroxide (ROS) is produced in large quantity from fertilized eggs. The evolved H_2O_2 is used by eggs to strengthen their shells and decrease polyspermia. However, it seems that this helpful mechanism is also deleterious to the eggs themselves. In this study, we found that when *B. cucurbitae* lay eggs into *S. edule* fruits, a large amount of H_2O_2 is produced (3 mM) and in turn instigates production of more H_2O_2 and Nitric oxide (NO). This ROS combination kill eggs and first instar larvae. It was found that mRNA expression of crucial enzymes that are involved in H_2O_2 and NO production are up regulated after infestation.